

Development of Questionnaire for Collecting Views on Growth and Development of Secondary Teacher Education With Reference To Expansion, Quality and Societal Needs

Paper Submission: 16/08/2020, Date of Acceptance: 26/08/2020, Date of Publication: 27/08/2020

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.10817859

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Abstract

The development of a nation depends upon the status of the teachers in the society. Teacher education is associated with the professional training and education of the present and prospective teachers. Various problems such as lack of uniformity between the institutions in the country regarding minimum qualifications for the teacher educators, unequal opportunities, mushrooming growth of institutes, commercialization and privatization of teacher education, imbalance regarding the demand and supply of trained teachers and ignoring attitude of different secondary teacher education institutions regarding societal needs. Therefore, there is a great need to collect valuable views of teacher trainees, teacher educators and principals in systematic way on various issues related to secondary teacher education. The main objective of this paper is to develop a questionnaire for collecting views on growth and development of secondary teacher education with reference to expansion, quality and societal needs. This paper deals with process adopted for developing the questionnaire and also standardization process used for standardize the questionnaire in detail.

Keywords: Teacher Education, Development of Questionnaire, Standardization Process of Questionnaire.

Introduction

Teacher Education is associated with the professional training and education of the present and prospective in order to provide quality education. Teacher education program includes quality as well as quantity which best fits the societal needs. A teacher's education is never complete in terms of professional competence, but the quantity of teacher education changes to a great extent according to prevailing situation, time and need. (Mohanthy, 2003)

The popularity of B.Ed. course made teaching profession attractive because it enlarged the job opportunities for the teachers. Moreover, it highly contributed in the growth of self-financed secondary teacher education institutions. The mushrooming of teacher education institutions in India in general and Haryana in specific indicates imbalance between the demand & supply of teachers, teacher educators etc. Right to Education (2009) under the context of UEE led to increased demand of teachers in the country. Privatization of teacher education also led to commercialization's ill effects .i.e. auctioning of

Qualification
management quota seats, extra charges for annual and monthly fees, origin of non attending concept in education, charging penalty for absenteeism and high charge for stationery items, hostel and mess charges. In the race of unfair competition, institutions are indulge in making more and more profits, continuously neglecting the norms and standards setup by NCTE and other of Education (CTEs). The report revealed some significant findings concerned with the functioning of Colleges of Education which were summarized as following:

1. Most of the colleges had less than 50 per cent of required strength of faculty-academic as well as technical staff. Lack of direct recruitment in academic posts.
2. A little bit CTEs had undertaken research projects.
3. Many colleges had not availed central assistance; reported delay in the utilization of grants.
4. Faculty development restricted to just participation in some in-service training programmes.
5. Only 40 per cent of the selected colleges had undertaken curriculum material development.

Ansari (2019) studied the impact of new norms and standards of NCTE on quality of teacher education. She concluded that quality improvement is totally depending upon the effective regulations and its effective implementation in teacher education institutes.

Objective of the Study

To develop a questionnaire for collecting views on growth and development of secondary teacher education with reference to expansion, quality and societal needs..

Statistical Technique Used

In order to standardize the questionnaire, Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was rigorously used for exploratory factory analysis to get factors of the framed questions by the researcher. The Principal Component Analysis method with varimax rotation was used. To determine the number of factors with a load of over (.50) the Eigenvalue Criterion and Correlation Matrix were applied.

Development of Questionnaire

The following procedure was adopted by the researcher to develop the questionnaire:

Identification and Selection of Item

To construct a questionnaire, first of all, identification and selection of all possible items was done carefully by the researcher. An exhaustive literature review was made in this regard by the researcher.

Preparation of Initial Draft

An initial draft of closed ended questions consisting 55 questions was framed to obtain responses on three point scale i.e. to great extent; to some extent and not at all. Content of the questionnaire was developed and the questions were framed in such a way that would motivate the respondents to provide required information regarding various issues related to secondary teacher

regulating bodies. This indicated ignorance of the societal needs. As Department of School Education and Literacy, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Govt. of India (2011) reviewed teacher education in the 11th Five Year Plan (FYP) and represented a report on Evaluation of Colleges

education. Questions were framed precisely and clearly avoiding double, negative, annoying and embarrassing questions.

Preliminary Try-Out

In the next step, preliminary try-out was carried by giving questionnaires to ten principals, 30 teacher educators and 50 teacher trainees for getting feedback concerning with suitability of the questions regarding various components, contents, clarity, understanding and language. The impractical, irrelevant and ambiguous questions were modified or deleted as per the feedback.

Modification in Initial Draft and Preparation of Final Draft

The questionnaire was revised, modified as per the feedback and as per requirement, new questions were added by the researcher. After the modification, the final draft of the questionnaire with 33 questions was prepared in order to get required information regarding various issues related to secondary teacher education.

Final Try-Out

For the purpose of determining the item analysis and homogeneity of items, the preparative questionnaire was individually administered to randomly selected sample of 330 respondents comprising ten principals, 60 teacher educators and 260 teacher trainees .The responses were scored separately for each respondent and items were counted on the strength of weights given to three categories of replies.

Scoring of Questionnaire

Items of the questionnaire were framed in question form followed by three alternative responses under three point rating scale namely to great extent; to some extent and not at all. The selected respondents have to tick on appropriate response against the given questions. The scoring procedure was very simple. The given responses of all the selected respondents were scored on the basis of following scoring pattern of framed questions:

Table No. 1: Scoring Pattern for the Questions

Response	To great extent	To some extent	Not at all
Score	3	2	1

Result and Discussion of Exploratory Factor Analysis

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was rigorously used for exploratory factory analysis in order to get factors of the framed questions by the researcher. The Principal Component Analysis method with varimax rotation was used. To determine the number of factors with a load of over (.50) the Eigenvalue Criterion and Correlation Matrix were applied. To get rotated component matrix or factor matrix, principal component extraction with varimax rotation method

was applied on 30 questions in SPSS. The rotated component matrix is given below:

Table No. 2: Rotated Component Matrix

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
1. Whether the teacher plays satisfactory role in the present day Indian society?	-.213	-.082	-.341	.861	.106
2. Whether the status of growth and development of secondary teacher education in India is satisfactory?	-.155	-.109	-.266	.899	.057
3. Whether the status of growth and development of secondary teacher education in Haryana is satisfactory?	-.181	-.087	-.322	.858	.085
4. Whether providing teacher education is the responsibility of Government?	-.183	-.082	-.287	.864	.000
5. Whether the role played by Government of Haryana in the growth and development of secondary teacher education in the state is satisfactory?	-.006	.964	.069	-.026	-.026
6. Whether the role of NCTE in planning and regulating the secondary teacher education in the country is satisfactory?	-.006	.966	.091	-.020	-.019
7. Whether the affiliating universities put regular checks to ensure that the colleges of secondary teacher education strictly follow all the prescribed norms and standards?	-.017	.787	.043	-.056	.092
8. Whether the mushrooming growth of teacher education institutions has positive qualitative impact on teacher education?	.921	-.095	.152	-.161	.059
9. Whether secondary teacher education has become easily accessible to all after the proliferation of teacher education institutions?	.965	-.060	.135	-.140	.057
10. Whether the proliferation of secondary teacher education in the state of Haryana ensures quality in teacher education programme?	.965	-.051	.129	-.139	.048
11. Whether the expansion of secondary teacher education would help in serving the social cause of educating the masses?	.092	-.066	.058	-.229	.031
12. Whether the quality of secondary teacher education being provided in the institutions of Haryana is up to the mark?	.955	.014	.102	-.137	.020
13. Whether 'nobility of profession and serving the society' motivates trainees to pursue B.Ed. course?	.966	.002	.108	-.140	.044
14. Whether only merit at the qualifying exams should be the satisfied admission criteria for secondary teacher education course (B.Ed.)?	.956	-.032	.128	-.128	.059
15. Whether both entrance test and marks of qualifying exams should be the satisfied admission criteria for secondary teacher education course (B.Ed.)?	.948	.024	.084	-.171	.036
16. Does the recent increased duration of B.Ed. course affect the quality of secondary teacher education programme positively?	.954	-.016	.120	-.140	.047
17. Do you favor the private participation in secondary teacher education?	.079	-.001	.034	-.063	.870
18. Whether allowing private participation in secondary teacher education would always lead to commercialization?	.090	.024	-.008	-.044	.901
19. Whether the managements of self-financed institutions of secondary teacher education appoint well qualified faculty on regular full time basis?	.035	.061	.049	-.038	.928
20. Whether privately managed self-financed institutions of secondary teacher education give salaries and other allowances to the teacher educators as per the UGC/ affiliating universities norms?	.065	.041	.039	-.057	.925

<i>Analysis</i>					
21. Whether the development of secondary teacher education in Haryana has been according to our societal needs?	.133	.024	.896	-.239	.020
22. Whether you favor the implementation of the policy of reservation for the underprivileged classes in secondary teacher education?	.141	.065	.937	-.268	.001
23. Whether the participation of students belonging to rural areas in the secondary teacher education in Haryana has been satisfactory?	.147	.078	.919	-.267	-.016
24. Whether secondary teacher education institutions in Haryana provide any type of concessions or incentives to the needy and deserving students?	.160	.074	.888	-.271	-.027
25. Whether the present curriculum of secondary teacher education programme has been designed according to our societal needs?	.160	.041	.901	-.268	.025
26. Whether the measures need to be taken by the Government for maintaining the balance between demand and supply of secondary teachers?	-.021	.966	.050	-.002	-.050
27. Whether the role played by NAAC-NCTE collaboration in ensuring the quality of secondary teacher education in the country is satisfactory?	-.015	.984	.588	-.016	.020
28. Whether lack of proper manpower planning is responsible factor for the mismatch between demand and supply of secondary teachers?	-.035	.943	.051	.001	-.031
29. Whether mushrooming growth of self financing institutes in the state widened huge gap between demand and supply of secondary teachers?	-.038	.965	.050	-.008	-.059
30. Whether increased duration of internship has positive qualitative impact on secondary teacher education course (B.Ed.)?	.113	.093	.886	-.202	-.009
31. Whether only entrance exam should be the satisfied admission criteria for secondary teacher education course (B.Ed.)?	-.038	.575	-.033	.019	.125
32. Whether 'job market value' motivates trainees to pursue B.Ed. course?	.082	-.044	.183	-.300	.086
33. Whether huge profits for the management are responsible factor for the proliferation of profit oriented institutes of secondary teacher education in the state?	.001	-.029	-.064	.137	.426

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

Interpretation

The above table shows the component matrix or factor matrix. It shows the coefficient used to express the standardized variables in terms of the factors. These coefficients, the factor loading, represent the correlation between the component or

factor and variables. The large value of coefficient represents that the factor and the variable are closely related. Out of 33 items those have below 0.6 values were rejected and the values above 0.6 were selected. In this way 29 items were selected which were divided in to 5 factors.

Table No. 3: Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
1. Whether the teacher plays satisfactory role in the present day Indian society?	1.000	.921
2. Whether the status of growth and development of secondary teacher education in India is satisfactory?	1.000	.919
3. Whether the status of growth and development of secondary teacher education in Haryana is satisfactory?	1.000	.887
4. Whether providing teacher education is the responsibility of Government?	1.000	.972
5. Whether the role played by Government of Haryana in the growth and development of secondary teacher education in the state is satisfactory?	1.000	.935
6. Whether the role of NCTE in planning and regulating the secondary teacher education in the country is satisfactory?	1.000	.942
7. Whether the affiliating universities put regular checks to ensure that the colleges of secondary teacher education to strictly follow all the prescribed norms and standards?	1.000	.633

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8. Whether the mushrooming growth of teacher education institutions has positive qualitative impact on teacher education?	1.000	.909
9. Whether secondary teacher education has become easily accessible to all after the proliferation of teacher education institutions?	1.000	.975
10. Whether the proliferation of secondary teacher education in the state of Haryana ensures quality in teacher education programme?	1.000	.973
11. Whether the expansion of secondary teacher education would help in serving the social cause of educating the masses?	1.000	.070
12. Whether the quality of secondary teacher education being provided in the institutions of Haryana is up to the mark?	1.000	.941
13. Whether 'nobility of profession and serving the society' motivates trainees to pursue B.Ed. course?	1.000	.967
14. Whether only merit at the qualifying exams should be the satisfied admission criteria for secondary teacher education course (B.Ed.)?	1.000	.951
15. Whether both entrance test and marks of qualifying exams should be the satisfied admission criteria for secondary teacher education course (B.Ed.)?	1.000	.937
16. Does the recent increased duration of B.Ed. course affect the quality of secondary teacher education programme positively?	1.000	.947
17. Do you favor private participation in secondary teacher education?	1.000	.768
18. Whether allowing private participation in secondary teacher education would always lead to commercialization?	1.000	.822
19. Whether the managements of self-financed institutions of secondary teacher education appoint well qualified faculty on regular full time basis?	1.000	.870
20. Whether privately managed self-financed institutions of secondary teacher education give salaries and other allowances to the teacher educators as per the UGC/ affiliating universities norms?	1.000	.865
21. Whether the development of secondary teacher education in Haryana has been according to our societal needs?	1.000	.879
22. Whether you favor the implementation of the policy of reservation for the underprivileged classes in secondary teacher education?	1.000	.974
23. Whether the participation of students belonging to rural areas in the secondary teacher education in Haryana has been satisfactory?	1.000	.945
24. Whether the secondary teacher education institutions in Haryana provide any type of concessions or incentives to the needy and deserving students?	1.000	.894
25. Whether the present curriculum of secondary teacher education programme has been designed according to our societal needs?	1.000	.911
26. Whether the measures need to be taken by the Government for maintaining the balance between demand and supply of secondary teachers?	1.000	.847
27. Whether the role played by NAAC-NCTE collaboration in ensuring the quality of secondary teacher education in the country is satisfactory?	1.000	.869
28. Whether lack of proper manpower planning is responsible factor for the mismatch between demand and supply of secondary teachers?	1.000	.894
29. Whether mushrooming growth of self financing institutes in the state widened huge gap between demand and supply of secondary teachers?	1.000	.940
30. Whether increased duration of internship has positive qualitative impact on secondary teacher education course (B.Ed.)?	1.000	.938
31. Whether only entrance exam should be the satisfied admission criteria for secondary teacher education course (B.Ed.)?	1.000	.349
32. Whether 'job market value' motivates trainees to pursue B.Ed. course?	1.000	.140
33. Whether huge profits for the management are responsible factor for the proliferation of profit oriented institutes of secondary teacher education in the state?	1.000	.205

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Interpretation

The above table shows the initial communalities and extraction communalities of variables or items which were defined as the sum of squared factor loadings for the variables. The large value of extraction communalities were well represented in the common factor space and low

value of extraction communalities were not well represented in the common factor space. Out of 33 items, Item no.11, 31, 32 & 33 were rejected because these have communalities below .05 and the values above 0.5 were selected. In this way 29 items were selected which were divided in to 5 factors.

Table No. 4: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen values	Extraction sums of squared loadings	Rotated sums of squared loadings
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<i>Anafisation</i>	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	10.340	31.332	31.332	10.340	31.332	31.332	7.575	22.956	22.956
2	6.894	20.891	52.223	6.894	20.891	52.223	6.624	20.073	43.029
3	4.565	13.835	66.058	4.565	13.835	66.058	5.475	16.592	59.621
4	3.421	10.366	76.424	3.421	10.366	76.424	3.765	11.410	71.031
5	1.768	5.359	81.783	1.768	5.359	81.783	3.548	10.753	81.783
6	.985	2.984	84.767						
7	.899	2.724	87.490						
8	.845	2.562	90.052						
9	.692	2.097	92.149						
10	.417	1.264	93.413						
11	.335	1.014	94.427						
12	.247	.747	95.174						
13	.232	.703	95.877						
14	.195	.591	96.468						
15	.160	.485	96.953						
16	.146	.442	97.395						
17	.132	.400	97.796						
18	.099	.301	98.097						
19	.082	.249	98.346						
20	.076	.231	98.577						
21	.071	.214	98.791						
22	.067	.204	98.995						
23	.053	.162	99.156						
24	.051	.155	99.311						
25	.044	.132	99.444						
26	.041	.124	99.567						
27	.033	.099	99.666						
28	.030	.091	99.757						
29	.027	.083	99.840						
30	.021	.064	99.904						
31	.019	.057	99.962						
32	.011	.033	99.995						
33	.002	.005	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Interpretation

The above table shows the extracted factor with factor loading and total variance explained in terms of extracted sums of squared loadings and the rotated sums of squared loadings. Eigen value represents sum of squared factor loading for a given factor which describes how much variance is

observed or being explained by that possible factor. It is defined as the variances of the factors. The factor have eigen value more than 1 is selected. The table indicates that there are five factors with Eigen value more than one. The total cumulative percentage of variance encountered for five factors is 81.783.

Analisation

Interpretation

Scree plot is the graphical representation of extracted factors which is used to show Eigen values of extracted factors. The above scree plot indicates

that first five factors have Eigen values more than one. As shown in the graph five factors have been extracted on the basis of prior knowledge for describing relationships among the variables in best way (B. Thomson, 2004).

Table No. 5: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.880	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	17626.547
	Df	528
	Sig.	.000

Interpretation

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) is a measure of sampling adequacy which was done to test or measure the homogeneity of variables and Bartlett's test of sphericity was used to test for the correlation among the variables used. The KMO value needs to

be over 0.60 and it could be accepted as sufficient as it is close to 0.90 (Nunnally, 1978). The above table shows 0.880 scale value which is acceptable for the present study. The Bartlett's test of sphericity shows significant results. Hence, the questionnaire was accepted.

Validity

Validity is concerned with the effectiveness as well as the success of a tool in measuring the specific property that is intended to be measured. The tool is valid if it measures what it intends to measure. (Kothari, 2004)

In order to standardize the questionnaire, the researcher established content validity of the questionnaire by showing it to experts concerned with the relevant field. Content validity is concerned with the extent to which a measuring tool provides adequate coverage of the topic under study. The draft of questionnaire was properly checked by the panel of experts and the questionnaire was altered and revised according to the given suggestions by the experts.

Reliability

Reliability is concerned with consistency. The tool is said to be reliable if it provides consistent results. Reliability as the degree to which a particular technique applied repeatedly to the same object, would produce the same result each time. For this purpose internal consistency of variables by Cronbach's Alpha method was used to determine the reliability of questionnaire in SPSS. Cronbach's Alpha developed by Lee Cronbach in 1951 as a measure of internal consistency, that is, how closely related a set of items are as a group (Mishra, & Bhaskar, 2010).

Reliability of extracted factors was calculated by the researcher in SPSS. Cronbach's Alpha method

was used to calculate internal consistency of the variables in each factor. The following table shows calculated Cronbach's Alpha Value for each factor:

Table No. 6: Reliability Statistics of Extracted Factors

Factor	No of items	Cronbach's Alpha Value
F-1	08	.992
F-2	07	.980
F-3	06	.979
F-4	04	.965
F-5	04	.937

Interpretation

In the above table, Cronbach alpha value indicates internal consistency of the each factor or construct. In general, a score of more than 0.7 is usually ok. Cronbach's Alpha value is greater or equal

to 0.9 indicates excellent internal consistency as a rule of thumb (Nunnally, 1978). The above table indicated that all the five extracted factors have high value (> 0.7) which represents good reliability of the data.

Table No. 7: Item-Total Statistics

Factor	Items under factor	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
F-1	Whether the quality of secondary teacher education being provided in the institutions of Haryana is up to the mark?	14.2129	28.673	.958	.991
	Whether 'nobility of profession and serving the society' motivate trainees to pursue B.Ed. course?	14.2097	28.606	.977	.990
	Whether only merit at the qualifying exams should be the satisfied admission criteria for secondary teacher education course (B.Ed.)?	14.1968	28.424	.967	.991
	Whether both entrance test and marks of qualifying exams should be the satisfied admission criteria for secondary teacher education course (B.Ed.)?	14.2097	28.723	.955	.991
	Does the recent increased duration of B.Ed. course affect the quality of secondary teacher education programme positively?	14.2194	28.534	.965	.991
	Whether the mushrooming growth of teacher education institutions has positive qualitative impact on teacher education?	14.2000	28.588	.936	.992
	Whether secondary teacher education has become easily accessible to all after the proliferation of teacher education institutions?	14.2194	28.275	.983	.990
	Whether the proliferation of secondary teacher education in the state of Haryana ensures quality in teacher education programme?	14.2258	28.324	.982	.990
F-2	Whether the role played by NAAC-NCTE collaboration in ensuring the quality of secondary teacher education in the country is satisfactory?	13.5663	12.409	.981	.972
	Whether the role played by Government of Haryana in the growth and development of secondary teacher education in the state is satisfactory?	13.5599	12.481	.958	.974
	Whether the role of NCTE in planning and regulating the secondary teacher education in the country is satisfactory?	13.5696	12.525	.962	.974
	Whether the affiliating universities put regular checks to ensure that the colleges of secondary teacher education to strictly follow all the prescribed norms and standards?	13.5761	13.271	.733	.989
	Whether lack of proper manpower planning is responsible factor for the mismatch between demand and supply of secondary teachers?	13.6084	12.538	.921	.976

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	Whether mushrooming growth of self financing institutes in the state widened huge gap between demand and supply of secondary teachers?	13.5955	12.423	.960	.974
	Whether the measures need to be taken by the Government for maintaining the balance between demand and supply of secondary teachers?	13.5922	12.457	.958	.974
F-3	Whether the development of secondary teacher education in Haryana has been according to our societal needs?	9.2387	3.289	.908	.977
	Do you favor the implementation of the policy of reservation for the underprivileged classes in secondary teacher education?	9.2516	3.341	.980	.970
	Whether the participation of students belonging to rural areas in the secondary teacher education in Haryana has been satisfactory?	9.2548	3.356	.958	.972
	Whether the secondary teacher education institutions in Haryana provide any type of concessions or incentives to the needy and deserving students?	9.2484	3.359	.920	.976
	Whether the present curriculum of secondary teacher education programme has been designed according to our societal needs?	9.2387	3.315	.934	.974
	Whether increased duration of internship has positive qualitative impact on secondary teacher education course (B.Ed.)?	9.2355	3.359	.882	.979
F-4	Whether the teacher play satisfactory role in the present day Indian society?	6.7516	1.747	.935	.948
	Whether the status of growth and development of secondary teacher education in India is satisfactory?	6.7516	1.695	.932	.949
	Whether the status of growth and development of secondary teacher education in Haryana is satisfactory?	6.7581	1.731	.903	.957
	Do you think that providing teacher education is the responsibility of Government?	6.7774	1.721	.886	.962
F-5	Do you favor private participation in secondary teacher education?	6.2548	1.116	.801	.934
	Whether allowing private participation in secondary teacher education would always lead to commercialization?	6.2677	1.109	.852	.916
	Whether the managements of self-financed institutions of secondary teacher education appoint well qualified faculty on regular full time basis?	6.2871	1.118	.879	.908
	Whether privately managed self-financed institutions of secondary teacher education give salaries and other allowances to the teacher educators as per the UGC/ affiliating universities norms?	6.2839	1.117	.870	.911

Interpretation

The above table shows Item- Total Statistics comprising scale mean, scale variance, corrected item-total correlation and cronbach's alpha if items deleted for each variable of extracted factors. The

table shows that under each factor the value of Cronbach alpha of variables/ items is continuously declining if the items deleted which indicated that each item/variable is important to maintain the desired Cronbach's alpha.

Table No. 8: Component wise Distribution of Final Questionnaire

Sr. No.	Components	No. of Questions	Total
1	General Status of Secondary Teacher Education	1,2,3,4	04
2	Role of Regulating Authorities and Affiliating Universities	5,6,7,8,9,10,11	07
3	Quality of Secondary Teacher Education	12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19	08
4	Privatization/Commercialization	20,21,22,23	04
5	Needs of the Society	24,25,26,27,28,29	06

Conclusion

In this way, final questionnaire was developed by the researcher with 29 close ended questions which was used to collect views on various issues concerning secondary teacher education covering the above said components.

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